

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Properties of Pyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-diones

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Only scanty reports^{1,2} on the synthesis of pyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolines have appeared in the literature, although this system is important in view of the presence of its isomer pyrimido[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline ring in the naturally occurring flavins. Moreover, nucleoside antibiotics formycin and formycin B have the pyrazolopyrimidine structure³. A metabolite of formycin and formycin B was characterised as a pyrazolopyrimidin-5,7-dione derivative, and 1-ethyl-6,7-methylenedioxy-4(1*H*)-oxocinnolin-3-carboxylic acid⁴ is a urinary tract antibacterial. This prompted us to optimise the reaction conditions for ring annulation of different 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamides and to investigate the antimicrobial activity of the hitherto unreported pyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-2,4-(1*H*,3*H*)-diones.

Results and Discussion

Pyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-one is synthesised by the cyclisation of 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide with formamide¹. For the present synthesis, 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamides (**3a-d**) have been prepared by the cyclisation of arylhydrazoano(cyano)-acetamides (**2a-d**) with anhydrous aluminium chloride in chlorobenzene¹. 2-Mercaptopyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-4(3*H*)-one (**4a-d**) were synthesised from **3a-d** by the reported procedure². Oxidative hydrolysis of compound **4a** using ammonium hydroxide and 30% hydrogen peroxide resulted in the replacement of the mercapto group by the hydroxyl group to yield pyrimido[5,4-*c*]cinnolin-2,4-(1*H*,3*H*)-dione (**5a**) (path a, Scheme 1). The reaction takes place probably through the intermediate formation of ammonium sulphonate group which is a much better leaving group than the thiol or methylthio group. The spectral

Scheme 1

and analytical data of the compounds are in good agreement with the structure assigned.

Scheme 2

The mass spectrum of **5a** gave a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 214 and this peak is also the base

peak. Like many other compounds of this type^{5,6}, the fragmentation proceeds (Scheme 2) with initial loss of HNCO furnishing fragment A_1 at m/z 171, which on further loss of CO gave fragment A_2 at m/z 143. The peak at m/z 117 corresponding to fragment A_3 is due loss of HNCO, CO and N_2 from M^+ . This fragment then decomposes eliminating HCN to afford A_4 at m/z 90. Loss of H^+ from A_4 results in A_5 at m/z 89. The above oxidative hydrolysis was found to be general, since the extension of the reactions to different derivatives of mercaptopyrimidocinnolinones (**4b-d**) yielded pyrimidocinnolindiones (**5b-d**). The structure **5a** was further confirmed by its synthesis through an independent route (path b, Scheme 1). 4-Aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide was fused with urea at 200° to give **5a** which was characterised by analytical and spectral data. Another method for the preparation of compound **5a** was attempted by refluxing 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide (**3a**) with ethyl chloroformate. The yellowish white product (**5a**) on treatment with cold sodium hydroxide solution (path c, Scheme 1) regenerated the initial 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide (**3a**). The ease at which the solid derivative transforms to the initial carboxamide itself, suggests the formation of a salt **7** with ethyl chloroformate, as envisaged in the corresponding quinolines⁷.

All the compounds (**5a-d**) were screened for antimicrobial activity against Gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cirrflagels*, Gram negative bacteria *Esherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas mandica* and the fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans* at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ using the cup-plate method⁸. The results reveal that the products are moderately active; generally the minimum inhibitory concentration was only 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Varian mat CH-7 (Finigan mat 8230 GC-MS) and RMU-GL Hitachi spectrometers. All solvents were distilled and dried according to literature procedures.

Arylhydrazono(cyano)acetamides (**2a-d**) were prepared by known methods⁹. Aminocinnoline carboxamides (**3a-d**) were prepared¹ from **2a-d**, and 2-mercaptopyrimido[5,4-c]cinnoline-4(3H)-ones (**4a-d**) were prepared as reported earlier².

Pyrimido[5,4-c]cinnolin-2,4(1H,3H)-diones (5a-d). Path a : Hydrogen peroxide (0.5 mmol; 30%) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of **4a-d** (5 mol) in ammonium hydroxide (20 ml; 28%) at 25°. After 1.5 h, the solution was acidified with acetic acid. The resulting solid was dissolved in hot dilute NaOH solution and then acidified with acetic acid. The compound was crystallised from DMSO, yields 54-64% : **5a**, m.p. >350; v_{max} 3 150, 3 050 (NH), 1 718, 1 703 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 11.5-11.73 (1H, brs, NH), 7.68-8.62 (4H, m, ArH); m/z 214(M^+); **5b-d**, m.ps. 300°.

Pyrimido[5,4-c]cinnolin-2,4(1H,3H)-diones (5a-d). Path b : 4-Aminocinnolin-3-carboxamides (**3a-d**; 2.8 mmol) were added to molten urea (1 g, 16.5 mmol) heated at 150° and the temperature was raised to 200° over a period of 15 min. The mixture was kept at 200-210° for an additional 50 min, whereupon crystallisation occurred. The product was diluted with water, acidified with HCl to pH 4-6 and the insoluble material separated by filtration, was dissolved in dilute aqueous NaOH and acidified with acetic acid. The resulting solid was separated and recrystallised from DMSO, yields 29-34% : **5a**, m.p. > 350°; v_{max} 3 150, 3 050 (NH), 1 720, 1 705 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 11.53, 11.73 (1H, brs, NH), 7.65-8.60 (4H, m, ArH); m/z 214(M^+); **5b-d**, > m.ps. 350°.

Treatment of 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide with ethyl chloroformate. Path c : A mixture of 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide (1 g, 5.32 mmol) and ethyl chloroformate (20 ml) was refluxed for 22 h, then cooled and the product formed, was filtered to give a yellowish-white solid, m.p. > 350°. Treatment of the solid with cold 5 N NaOH regenerated 4-aminocinnolin-3-carboxamide (**3a**; 0.80 g, 80%).

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